

Diterpenoids

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Investigations during the last forty years on the basis of the "Isoprene rule" have resulted in the elucidation of the structure, stereochemistry, and in many cases the absolute configuration of a large number of terpenoids due, no doubt to the development of infrared and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, spectropolarimetry, mass spectrography, and vapour phase chromatography. These powerful physical tools have recently revealed many a finer aspect of the molecular patterns hitherto unsuspected in related fields.

It is proposed to restrict this review to recent advances in diterpenoids excluding, however, the diterpenoid alkaloids'. Diterpenoids can be classified as being built up of four C_5 units representing a wide class of naturally occurring compounds, such as acids, alcohols, lactones, ethers, and furanoids, besides hydrocarbons. One of the most intensively studied members of this group is abietic acid, the molecular framework of which was clearly established in 1941; but this could not be fitted into the isoprene rule. A few isomers were then known and in some, a different carbon skeleton had also been established at that time. Until recently the entire field was considered to be extremely complicated because of inadequate understanding of the rearrangements that were generally associated with these types of molecules. More recently, a large variety of diterpenoids have been isolated not only from the plant kingdom but also from mould metabolites. It has now become possible to systematise hitherto-unrelated compounds from a well-ordered C_{20} -chain on experimentally documented reaction mechanisms. A close inspection of these types suggests common mechanistic features in spite of apparent diversity. The most cardinal one in the entire mechanistic spectrum is the migration of quaternary methyl groups to adjacent positions in carbocyclic systems. On this basis, these may broadly be classified, as shown below, taking into account some representative members of each category.

Classification

(1) *Open-chain:*

Phytol
(I)

(2) *Carbocyclic rings*: (i) *Monocyclic* (II and III); (ii) *Bicyclic* (IV) sclareol, manool, agantheme-dicarboxylic acid, marrubiin, eperuic acid, labdanolic acid, cativic acid, and ketolabdanolic acid⁵.

Axerophthol or Vitamin A
(II)

Camphorene²
(III)

(IV)

The carbon framework of columbin⁴ originates from migration of two quaternary methyl groups at C₇- and C_{4b}- to adjacent positions, C_{10a}- and C_{4b}- respectively (cf. iii (f) *vide infra* and Friedelin⁵).

(iii) *Tricyclic*

(VI)

(a) *Pimanthrene series*, i.e., affording pimanthrene on dehydrogenation.

(VII): R = vinyl, Δ 8(8a)

(VIII): R = -CHOH.CH₂OH, Δ 8a(8)

Pimanic acid (dextro⁶-pimanic acid), 4b- α (H), 7- β (vinyl). Isopimanic acid (isodextro⁶-pimanic acid), 4b- β (H), 7- α (vinyl).⁷ Sandaracopimanic acid (C₇-epimer of pimanic acid)⁸. Cryptopimanic acid (formerly considered to be C_{4b}-epimer^{9a} of pimanic acid)^{9b}.

Migration of methyl (C₇ $\rightarrow$ C₁₄) evidently through carbonium ion mechanism, subsequently realised experimentally by Wenkert¹⁰.

(IX)

(b) *Retene series*, i. e., affording retene or its derivatives on dehydrogenation.

Abietic acid ⁷ ,	Δ^7 (8), 8a(9)
Neoabietic acid ⁷ ,	Δ^7 (14), 8(8a)
Palustic acid ⁷ ,	Δ^{4b} (8a), 7(8)
Teloabietic acid ^{7,12} ,	Δ^7 (8), 14(15)

(c) *Migration of methyl* ($C_7 \rightarrow C_8$) *inside the ring.*

Vinhaticoic and vouacapenic acids are epimeric at C_1 .

(d) *Loss of isopropyl group.*

(e) *Loss of C₇-ethyl group.* Nimbiol ($R_2=R_1=Me$, $R_3=O$ in XVI),

(f). *Migration of C_{4a}-methyl group* (cf. γ -lactone from dihydropimaric acid)¹⁰,

Roscnolactones¹³
(XVII)

(iv) *Tetracyclic*

Mirene
(XVIII)

(b) *Migration of c₇-methyl group.*

Phyllocladene, steviol
(XIX)

(c) *Loss of C_{4a}-methyl group* and subsequent contraction of the ring.

Gibberellins¹⁴
(XX)

CO₂H group originates from C₉- and this has been established through tracer technique¹⁵.

(d) *Migration of methyl (C₁ → C₁₁; cf. methylabietin¹⁶)* to form the ethyl chain. This accounts for the skeleton of cafestol and kahwiol and the ethyl chain forms a furan ring involving the oxygenated C₂- position.

(XXI)

Resin acids can again be classified into two fundamental groups depending on stereochemistry of C_1 -carboxyl with respect to C_{4a} -methyl group. In abietic acid and pimaric acid, it is α - and in podocarpic acid and aganthe dicarboxylic acid, it is β -. Biogenetically this may be of great taxonomical interest, but from synthetic studies (*vide infra*) this is also quite significant. Chemically, it has been possible to develop diagnostic methods to differentiate the stereochemistry of the carboxyl groups. The classical method of alkaline hydrolysis¹⁷ has so long been utilised to differentiate this system, as the β -oriented ester group is very difficult to hydrolyse except under drastic experimental conditions. Recently two other methods have also been found applicable for this purpose. One is due to Wenkert and Jackson¹⁸. The β -oriented ester group is converted into the carboxyl with lithium and liquid ammonia and the α -oriented ester group is reduced to the primary alcohol. Another ingenious method¹⁹ through determination of the apparent dissociation constants of the isomeric acids has been successfully developed by Prof. Prelog in Zürich. The pK value of the β -oriented carboxyl group is (8.4-8.5) and that of α -oriented carboxyl group is (8.0-8.1).

Biogenesis

In 1956, Cocker *et al.*²⁰ proposed a hypothesis that the biogenesis of di- and tri-terpenoids is based on different mechanisms. Cyclisation of polyene chain for the formation of diterpenoids was supposed to proceed through participation of protons. Their main arguments were the non-occurrence of di- and tri-terpenoids together in plants and also diterpenoids having no hydroxyl function at C_2 . Isolation²¹ of nimbin and nimbiol from *Melia azadirachta*, Linn. is a unique observation. Another significant factor that has emerged during these studies is that in recently isolated C_2 -hydroxyditerpenoids and in eperuic acid, C_{4a} -methyl has an absolute configuration opposite to that present in C_2 -non-oxygenated diterpenoids, triterpenoids and steroids. A new comprehensive biogenetic scheme has got to be evolved which can offer a unifying concept emphasising the common origin of terpenoids and steroids. In this connection, it is worth mentioning that molecular oxygen²², and not the OH^+ originally proposed by Ruzicka, is the effective initiator in the cyclisation of polyenes for the biosynthesis of polyisoprenoids.

Coming to the more specific examples, it is to be noted that ring C is attended with aromatisation at some stage of the phytochemical oxidation with concomitant introduction of hydroxyl at C_6 -. In this connection the presence of hinokiol is quite significant. It may be interesting to suggest the following pathway for the loss of isopropyl group leading to podocarpic acid.

This is quite analogous to that suggested for the biogenesis of furan derivatives²³. This again brings in line with the mechanism put forward by Sen Gupta *et al.*²¹ for the loss of ethyl group resulting in nimbiol. This circumvents the role of steric factors inherent in the mechanism proposed by Wenkert²⁴. It fails to explain, however, the migration of isopropyl

group leading to the structure of totarol, whereas the mechanism suggested by Wenkert appears to be quite novel. It may be worthwhile to suggest that the migration of isopropyl takes place through the formation of a cyclopropane derivative followed by oxidative fission. A close analogy may be found in the partial structure of zierone²⁵ (XXVIII)

where the isopropyl group has migrated to the neighbouring position evidently through a cyclopropane intermediate. Recently, quite a few analogous compounds, maaliol (XXIX), aromadendrene (XXX), and cycloclorenone (XXXI), have been isolated and the fission of the cyclopropane ring in the desired direction has also been achieved.

It may be emphasised here that no diterpenoid with a cyclopropane ring has so far been isolated from natural sources although triterpenoids containing cyclopropane ring are already known, e.g., cycloartenol, cyclolandenol and phyllanthol²⁶.

Synthesis

Synthetic studies in this field were far behind. Fruitful attempts in this direction have been initiated during the last few years. The apparent difficulty in the past had been the devising of suitable stereoselective methods with a view to avoiding the stereochemical complexities arising from lack of proper knowledge of their structures and stereochemistry. The earliest success in this field may be said to be the synthesis of phytol by Karrer²⁷. Attempts towards synthesis of the monocyclic derivatives, particularly vitamin-A, have been quite extensive, resulting in its total synthesis by Isler²⁸. In the bicyclic system, successful approaches have been made by Lederer²⁹ and particularly by Bartlop³⁰ for the synthesis of sclareol (XXXVI), methyl labdanolate (XXXV), its C₁₃-isomer, and (C₁₃-iso)-manoöl (XXXVII). Recently sclareol has been converted³¹ to manoöl.

A comprehensive series of experiments on the synthesis of terpenoids has been initiated in this laboratory since 1952 and some of the results achieved so far have been published³². Synthesis of the bicyclic ketone (XXXVIII) (semicarbazone, m.p. 221-22°) and of the keto-acid (XXXIX, m.p. 161°) of known stereochemistry have been accomplished (G. Banerjee, unpublished work) and these may be looked upon as important building units towards the synthesis of bicyclic diterpenoids.

With a view to synthesising marrubiin, attempts were made (S. L. Mukherjee, D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1959) to obtain the ketolactone (XL) through cyclisation of the acid (XLI) with polyphosphoric acid. A crystalline product, m.p. 159-60°, was isolated in

poor yield; to this the structure (XLII) has been tentatively assigned on the basis of infrared studies and the highly hindered nature of the carbonyl group. The unusual course of this ring-closure led us to investigate cyclisation of the acid (XLIII) under similar conditions (P.K. Ramachandran, D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1960); this again afforded a mixture of 5- and 6-membered ketones as revealed through infrared studies, with the five-membered one predominating. Cyclisation of the acid (XLIV), however, leads to the expected 6-membered ketone. It is quite evident that acid-catalysed cyclisation and intramolecular acylation proceed along two different mechanistic pathways. The tacit idea that steric factor associated with *gem*-disubstituted grouping might be responsible for the fir-

mation of cyclopentane rings appears to be untenable*. For synthesising diterpenoids having the characteristic 'C₂-OH' group, the following bicyclic acetoxyketones (XLV)^{32g}, and (XLVI)^{32h} have been synthesised. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that these acetoxyketones might also serve as potential intermediates for the synthesis of triterpenoids.

Considerable success has been achieved towards the synthesis of diterpenoids, particularly with the ring C aromatic, and consequently having lesser number of asymmetric centres. Mention may be made in this connection of the synthesis of nimbiol^{32i, 33}, ferruginol³⁴, sugiol³⁵, totarol³⁶, *dl*-podocarpic acid^{32d, 37}, different isomers of desoxypodocarpic acid^{32d}, *dl*-dehydroabietic acid³⁸, and some of its stereoisomers^{32j}. A close analysis of the methods developed for the successful synthesis of these compounds reveals some interesting common features: (a) cyclisation of phenethylcyclohexenes or their precursors, (b) a suitably substituted octahydrophenanthrenes, and (c) fusion of the ring A to the corresponding tetralin derivatives leading to octahydrophenanthrenes. As mentioned earlier, synthesis of the racemic form of *dl*-podocarpic acid was realised long back and its identity with the natural podocarpic acid has recently been established. All the successful methods developed by Bhattacharyya, Haworth, and King³⁷ follow the same procedure (a). A serious drawback of this method is lack of sufficient control on stereochemistry at C₁- and formation of *cis* and *trans* isomeric mixtures with respect to A/B rings, evidently due to comparative stability of the tertiary carbonium ion generated through protonation of the double bond of the cyclohexene ring. In fact, it has not been possible to develop the desired stereochemistry (e. g. C_{1a}-Me: C₁-CO₂H *trans*) present in abietic acid systems from a suitably substituted phenethylcyclohexene derivatives. Next important development in this field is the synthesis of the tricyclic ketones³⁹.

(XLVII : R=H or Pr)

The presence of the α -decalone system in these ketones was assumed to lead to the *trans*- ring junction. The next phase of synthetic studies stems with the development of suitable methods for converting carbonyl to *gem*-methyl-carboxyl function. Two methods^{32c}, complementary to each other, have been successfully developed utilising cyclohexanone as a model compound. It was expected that in the case of unsymmetrical tricyclic ketones,

*The formation of the cyclopentane derivative is preferred as the formation of cyclohexane ring is diffi-

cult stereo-electronically (Spadling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1681).

these two methods would ultimately lead to epimers at C_4 because of the presence of the angular methyl group. Experiments in these directions led to the synthesis of an isomer of desoxypodocarpic acid (LIV) through the application of the method (i), but the second

method led to unexpected results which involved reduction of the double bond with the Grignard's reagent. This observation is a unique one as no β -hydrogen atom is available to explain the reducing property of methyl-Grignard reagent. This could only be explained by assuming that the intermediate transition complex had extracted hydrogen from ether which was present in the medium as solvent. An experimental verification of the hypothesis through the isolation of acetaldehyde via the hydrolytic fission of vinyl ether has so far failed. Incidentally, it might be mentioned that the tricyclic ketone (LVI) is a mixture of *cis* and *trans* forms (cf. N. N. Saha, D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1953) with *cis* one predominating and this was established experimentally through oxidative degradation⁴⁰.

The synthesis of two isomers^{32d} of desoxypodocarpic acid has been achieved as shown below.

The acid (LVI) was utilised for the synthesis of *dl*-podocarpic acid through the introduction of 6-hydroxyl through acetylation. For the synthesis of the remaining isomer, the procedure (c) had to be adopted and the process followed the same pattern as was utilised for the synthesis of dehydroabiatic acid. The synthesis of two other isomers of dehydroabiatic acid has recently been reported^{30j}.

The synthesis of a tricyclic compound (LVIII) with non-aromatic ring C and having functional groups, characteristic of the pimaric acid series has been achieved⁴¹.

In the tetracyclic system, no notable achievement has been made so far. Announcement of the recent synthesis of phyllocladinic acid, a degradation product of phyllocladene, has been reported⁴². Synthetic studies by Cross and coworkers⁴³ on gibberellic

(LVIII)

(LIX)

acid have been quite prolific evidently because of its pronounced physiological importance as a plant-growth factor.

In the microcosm of organic chemistry represented by terpenoids, the diterpenoids occupy a conspicuous place by the side of sesqui- and triterpenoids as the grandeur of the entire arena is now quite apparent as a result of recent investigations from theoretical, mechanistic, phytochemical, and synthetic aspects.

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